

THE IMPACT OF POLITICAL LITERATION ON POLITICAL MATURITY AND VOTING OF POLITICAL RIGHTS DECISION

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Abstract

Political literacy in Indonesia is now growing, which is indicated by the existence of a “political literacy movement” both from the government and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) both before the general election and after the activity. The set of abilities, sk elopment of political literacy towards the consolidation of democracy in Indonesia. The purpose of this study is to answer whether the mastery of political literacy and political maturity can be increased decision to use the political rights of voters. This study used is quantitative with a normative approach involving a sample of 185 voters registering in the final voter list for the general election in Kediri Regency in 2019. Data were collected using a questionnaire and was analyzed using the SPSS application. Political literacy has a positive impact on decisions to use political rights. Political maturity also has a positive impact on decisions on the use of political rights. Mastery of political literacy and political maturity simultaneously significantly influence the decision to use political rights. These findings indicate that political literacy and political maturity can be factors in increasing political participation in Indonesia.

Keywords: political literacy, political maturity, political rights, voting

1. Introduction

The development of political literacy in Indonesia is basically still low, so it requires increasing political literacy by conducting political socialization involving the government and non-governance organizations (NGO). Indonesia's status as the third largest democracy in the world with the largest Muslim population in the world has included active community participation, critical thinking, and democratic participation.

As defined by the American Political Science Association (APSA, 2022), political literacy is a set of abilities, skills, and knowledge deemed necessary for citizens to participate in the governance of a society. To participate in a democratic government, the following actions are required: (1) voting for public officials at all levels of government, from local to state level, (2) attending public meetings, also known as "political campaigns" and attending 'open house' activities. politics' to ask questions and obtain first-hand information, namely from public officials, (3) examine and evaluate the background and qualifications of presidential candidates to be elected, (4) evaluate the performance of elected officials by conducting research on the performance that has been achieved, (5) make recommendations for new laws and regulations, as well as changes to existing laws and regulations, and (6) research plans, programs, budgets, and their impact on improving people's welfare.

The electoral system in Indonesia is very unique. There are several reasons behind it, among others: first, political choices are more influenced by the political choices of religious figures

they adhere to, not from the track records of candidates for leadership. Second, money politics is far more dominant to whom political choices are given, not to the track records of candidates for leadership, so even if a former corruptor, if he can give a lot of money before the election, he will be the one who will be elected in the general election. Third, political socialization, political education, political campaigns, and political maturity that have been carried out with large costs and resources, which should have been able to improve the quality of general elections, can be easily damaged by "politics champions" who prioritize coercion of will through violence and threats, so that political choices are not influenced by these factors, but are more influenced by threats of violence because prospective voters have received money as collateral. Fourth, the contractors for the construction of physical facilities participate in financing the 'political costs' incurred by the candidates for leadership who are struggling, by hope to win the tender (auction) for the physical construction project.

This is what causes researchers to be very interested in conducting research in Indonesia as a research location. This finding, of course, can be applied anywhere, especially in developing countries that implement direct elections (one person one vote). The second reason, why this research can be applied in general everywhere, is because this research is a quantitative study with respondents determined by using an accurate sampling technique, so that the selected sample can represent the population responsibly. The instrument used has been calibrated using a valid method. By referring to the reasoning, it is believed that this research is very feasible to be generalized to a wider area beyond the research location.

Indonesia is a democratic country that respects its citizens' rights to tolerance without liberalism, including when elections are held for democratic parties like the general election and regional head election (Pemilukada) (Menchik, 2016). Elections for leadership candidates and regional head elections also give every citizen a chance to fight for their rights collectively. Since the democratization of the past twenty years, it is clear that the performance has improved (Davidson, 2018). However, research shows that constitutional democracy has deteriorated and political burdens have increased (Feith, 2006; Sondakh, 2014; Aspinall & Berenschot, 2019). Informal networks and electoral strategies have a far more profound impact on the allocation of power in government.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 21 paragraph (1), states that the state also gives another form of attention to its citizens, namely the right to vote and be elected (from now on referred to as active and passive voting rights). Active voting right is a decision to vote carried out by the community activities in determining the form of government administration by holding an election. Active voting rights are cross-border. Therefore anyone, in this case, every citizen, has the right to vote in the General Election.

Election/Pemilukada is a condition sine qua non for a modern democratic country, meaning that the people elect someone to represent them in the context of people's participation in the administration of state governance, temporarily handing over their political rights. This right is a sovereign right to participate in running the state administration (Budiarjo, 1990; Zazili, 2016). The implementation of people's sovereignty cannot be separated from the "Pemilukada" because "Pemilukada" is a logical consequence of adopting the principle of

people's freedom (democracy) in the nation and state. The basic principle of democratic state life is that every citizen can actively participate in the political process (Thaib, 1993) as in Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (UUD NKRI 1945) (Nasution & Marwandianto, 2019; Wisnaeni & Herawati, 2020).

The election process or result certainly raises questions, and some pessimists and considers it counterproductive to the due democratic process. One of the keywords that can minimize problems and increase benefits is the existence of political adolescence, at the level of political parties, political elites, election organizers, and at the mass level (Gunawan, 2008). This political maturity can increase through increasing political literacy and increasing awareness of democracy.

The means of exercising people's sovereignty; ideally, "Pemilukada" is not only followed by a large number of voters (quantity) so that the level of participation is high. But this also takes place in a competitive, transparent, fair, accountable atmosphere (quality), and can produce the choice of political leaders, involving the competent and with integrity. In other words, post-conflict local elections not only have high levels of participation but also have quality participation. They produce a quality post-conflict local election with high-quality involvement. Certain preconditions are required, one of which is the performance of voters who are politically literate, intelligent, and critical, so that their political preferences are rational (rational choice) (Sutisna, 2017). In this way, sound political preferences heavily influence by the political literacy they control.

The holding of simultaneous regional elections in 2020 will attend by 270 regions with details of 9 provinces, 224 districts, and 37 cities. The number of single candidates in the 2020 Pilkada increased to 31 areas. A very significant increase because in 2015, the number of regions that had a single candidate was only three regions; in 2017, there were nine regions, 2018 there were 16 regions. Especially in Kediri Regency, the 2020 "Pemilukada" only presents single candidate pairs, namely Hanandhito Hilmawan Praman-Dewi Mariya Ulfa, supported by PDIP, which currently has 15 seats and PKB with nine seats, Golkar 6 seats, Gerinda, and PAN 5 seats each, as well as the 4-seat Nasdem.

Political education to increase political literacy is a path to a reform process for rural people in their political life. Political education considers as an alternative in changing people's attitudes and behavior in a democracy. More than that, political education must be carried out for the people through knowledge transformation, the transformation of understanding of politics (Kimbal, 2018). Through political education, development progress will raise through political initiatives; the interests of development programs are not only acknowledged by the people. Still, they must be evaluated, controlled, and even given freedom in the policy-making process for development (Sastropoerto, 2014). According to Kartono (2011) political education for the people must be able to raise awareness and enthusiasm in dealing with political problems that are considered urgent, able to solve and avoid conflicts and insecurities in the community.

The intelligence and critical power of first-time voters through political education, various parties, especially the KPU and Bawaslu as election organizers, the government, and election participants (especially political parties), have made multiple efforts to educate voters (voter education), primarily through socialization activities. It's just that, due to the limitations of time-space, media and methods, these socialization activities have practically less significant impact on fostering the intelligence and critical power (political literacy) of new voters (Sutisna, 2017).

Theoretically, the spirit of democracy has not maximally accommodated explicitly. Article (56) Law no. 32 Years and Article (1) Government Regulation Number 6 the Year 2005, for example, emphasizes that pairs of candidates can only submit by political parties or coalitions of political parties. Various conflicts before and after the "Pemilukada" can only occur because of basic things, namely ideology or religion (Sondakh, 2014).

Another problem raised to date is the low awareness of using ballot in the form of political participation. Especially amid the Covid-19 pandemic, the majority of people, especially in urban areas and in areas that are still in the 'red zone,' are predicted to have a lot of people who are reluctant to come to polling stations to channel or exercise their political rights (Perludem, 2020). It said that politics in Indonesia has a responsible democracy but has flawed general elections (Bland, 2019). Therefore, according to researchers, it is necessary to study why this happened.

Previous studies have revealed that devout voters are more likely to participate in politics and serve as a protector against the long-term trend towards civil disengagement (Mujani, et. al., 2018). So far, the increase in voting rights (political participation) only uses appeals or persuasion. through this research, it is hoped that both independent and intermediate variables can found to increase the use of public voting in following the next Pilkada, significantly strengthening political literacy, raising awareness, democracy, and increasing the political maturity of the citizens.

The formulation of the research problem can be indicated as follows.

1. Is there any influence of political literacy on the decision to use political rights?
2. Is there any influence of political maturity on the decision to use political rights?
3. Is there a joint influence between political literacy and political maturity on the decision to use political rights?

2. Literature review

2.1. Political Literacy

Political literacy is a practical understanding of concepts taken from everyday life and language. It is an effort to understand political issues, the contestants' beliefs, how their tendencies affect themselves and others. In short, political literacy is a compound of knowledge, skills, and attitudes about politics (Bakti, 2012). Voters who are rational (intelligent and critical) can illustrate voters who do not only have electoral knowledge and

awareness (electoral). Free from various forms of intimidation and resistant to attack or unhealthy transactional persuasion. And also break the rules like money politics and fully understand the importance of the votes they have and the political consequences of their choices in the future (Watson, 2020). Irrational voters or voters who are "politically blind" (political illiteracy) contribute (have an impact) on the implementation and results of the election that are not qualified. Elections decorate with transactional practices such as money politics and mobilization. Elections that gave birth to more elected candidates (both legislative and executive elections) lack integrity and are far from competent (Sutisna, 2017).

Political literacy activities are a strategy for political learning or education, which is carried out through communication, attending seminars, seeing, reading and listening to political news and accompanied by positive activities for political education (Bekele & Ago 2020). Following discussion activities, political debates on television, various and reading political information on social media, millennial voters will be able to find out about political developments that are happening. Good political literacy will be able to increase political maturity (Bakhtiyar, 2018).

To be able to achieve political maturity, millennial voters always need political information, where political information must not be swallowed up, because it must be sought and analyzed for its truth and depth. In order to obtain up to date and valid political information, a variety of accurate and reliable sources of information are needed.

Theoretically, when political literacy is good, the level of decision to use their political rights will also be good, in the sense that they have an obligation to go to polling stations in order to give their voting rights in the form of political participation. On the other hand, if their political literacy is low, of course they will not feel guilty if they are not involved in the general election.

Therefore, to improve decisions on the use of political rights in the form of political participation, it is necessary to increase political literacy both through: 1) public service advertisements broadcast through television, radio, and print mass media, 2) online political socialization using social media, 3) small and medium scale campaigns, both closed and large in the open field, 4) political debates, 5) political campaigns, 6) social and political services, 7) political literacy movements, 8) associations or deliberation at the village level, 9) installation of banners in public places, and others

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant influence between political literacy on the decision to use political rights.

2.2. Political Maturity

Political maturity refers to the term political adolescent (political maturity) or political maturity (political maturity). These terms relate to the political attitude and political behavior of individuals and organizations (Krampen 2000). If political maturity means the political maturity of the ordinary people, then it must be understood from two perspectives first, what emerges from itself as an autonomous expression or objective condition of individuals,

second, which arises from (or a response to) the environment outside of itself (Gunawan, 2008).

Political maturity shows the attitude and behaviour of the gentle elite who are soft and have statesmanship. Political parties that are more oriented to process or process-results than results; election administrators who are fair, transparent, full of preparation (thorough), and more comprehensive. Increasingly professional election supervisors, facilitators who do not take sides and accept whatever the election results, the masses who have autonomous, non-violent participation not easily provoked, and electoral conflict resolution is carried out elegantly without violence. More profoundly, good political maturity can reflect individual behaviour in acting independently. On the contrary, political immaturity can undermine national political relations (Ahmetaj, 2019). The role of parties, election administrators, and the government is enormous in maturing the politics of ordinary people and other segments (including political parties, government, and political elites, etc.) (Gunawan, 2008).

Reading the description above, it can be understood that when political maturity increases, the decision to exercise political rights will also increase. Conversely, when political maturity is low, the decision to exercise political rights will also be low. So to improve decisions on the use of political rights, one of the strategies is to increase political maturity.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant effect of political maturity on the decision to use political rights.

2.3. Decision on the Use of Political Rights

Rahardjo argues that rights are the power to protect the interests of everyone given by law (Mas, 2004). This view affirms that rights are something that everyone has and is obliged to fulfill, including political rights (Bawamenewi, 2019). According to Heywood (2017), politics is an activity of a nation that aims to create, maintain, and amend general regulations governing its life. It cannot separate from the symptoms of conflict and cooperation (politics is the activity through which they live and inextricably linked to competition and collaboration). Meanwhile, Merkl (2015) said that politics, in its best form, is an effort to achieve a fair and just social order. Meanwhile, in its imperfect way, it is a struggle for power, position, and wealth for one's interests (politics at its worst is a selfish grab for energy and riches).

Thus, efforts to implement political rights for citizens other than the government are responsible for providing means of realizing and facilitating citizens' rights and giving supervision based on modes that reasonably suspect of being part of law violations. Citizens also have a share and must play a role in ensuring, see and question the government according to its level and channel its political rights according to the applicable mechanisms and regulations (Bawamenewi, 2019).

In the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, ICCPR (International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights) states that the existence of fundamental human rights and freedoms classified into two types: first, the neo Non-derogable rights category, namely

rights that are absolute and cannot be reduced, even in an emergency. This right consists of; (i) rights to life; (ii) the right to be free from torture (right to be free from slavery); (iii) the right to be free from detention due to failure of the agreement (debt); (iv) the right to be free from retroactive punishment, the right as a legal subject, and to freedom of thought, conscience, religion (Payne & Abouharb, 2016).

The second type is the Non-derogable rights category, namely rights that can be reduced/limited by the fulfillment of the state party. The rights and freedoms included in this type include (i) the right to freedom of peaceful assembly; (ii) the right to freedom of association, including forming and becoming members of labor; and (iii) the right to freedom of expression/expression; including the freedom to seek, receive, and provide information with all kinds of ideas without regard to boundaries (both orally / in writing) (Ivanova, 2019).

Reading the theoretical study above, it can be understood that when political literacy and political maturity simultaneously increase, the decision to use political rights will also increase. Conversely, when political literacy and political maturity simultaneously decline, the decision to use political rights will also decrease. Thus, to improve political decisions in general elections can be increased through increasing political literacy and political maturity simultaneously.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant influence between political literacy and political maturity simultaneously on the decision to use political rights.

3. Methodology

3.1. Design

This research approach is correlational quantitative research. Correlational research seeks to test hypotheses developed by relevant previous research results and test theories that have been produced by previous experts based on current data, and the results can strengthen or invalidate existing theories (Sudjarwo & Basrowi, 2009)

3.2. Participant

This research was conducted in Kediri Regency, especially during the 2019 General Election. The population of this study were all people of Kediri Regency who had voting rights in 2019, namely 1,308,864 (KPU, Kab. Kediri, 2020). The research sample was determined as many as 185 people. This number was chosen because it is based on the opinion of Hair et.al (2010) that the recommended sample size is 5-10 times the number of indicators. In this study, the number of indicators is 37. If the number of indicators is multiplied by five, then 185 samples are obtained.

3.3. Instrument

The instrument was prepared by the researcher with reference to the dimensions and indicators in the theory (Basrowi & Utami, 2019). The research instrument consisted of political literacy, political maturity, and decisions on the use of political rights. The political

literacy variable instrument consists of 3 dimensions, namely knowledge of political parties, general elections, and regional leader elections. These three dimensions are then developed into 6 indicators which are then compiled into 6 items of research instruments.

The instrument of political maturity variable consists of 2 dimensions, namely the dimension of awareness of using voting rights and awareness to elect regional leaders democratically. The two dimensions are then developed into 6 indicators, then arranged into 6 items of research instruments. The variable instrument for the decision to use political rights consists of 3 dimensions, namely: the determination of political choices, the enforcement of the democratization process, and the realization of honest elections. The three dimensions are then developed into 8 indicators. Then arranged into 8 items of research instruments. The total number of instrument items was 20 research instrument items. Furthermore, the instrument was compiled into the google form application, which was then distributed to voters in Kediri Regency, to see the level of political education, political awareness, political maturity, and awareness to exercise their political rights.

3.4. Data Collection

The primary method of data collection was through surveys, namely by distributing questionnaires to respondents (Basrowi & Utami, 2020). The instrument is distributed using the google form application. Respondents can fill in the instrument via a gadget (handphone), then send it to the researcher, so that the researcher can monitor, describe and quickly analyze the results of the data collection that has been done.

3.5. Data Analysis

The reliability of this research instrument was calculated using the Cronbach's Alpha formula. The calculation results are shown in the following table.

ills, and knowledge of citizens to participate in general elections has shown the dev

Table 1: The results of the research instrument reliability test

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach' alpha	Cronbach's Alpha based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.806	0,863	20

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

Based on the results of the reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha, it is known that the coefficient is $0.806 > 0.60$. Thus it can be concluded that the instrument has a high level of consistency. To determine the normality of the sample compared to the population, the researcher conducted the Kolmogorov Smirnov Z test. The results of the sample normality test showed that the sample was not significantly different from the population.

Table 2: Data Normality Test Results

Description	Unstandardized Residual
N	185

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	,872
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	,325

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

The results of the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnow Test normality test showed a significant value of Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) of 0.325 > 0.05, then the Kolmogorov-Smirnow normality test with data from 185 samples are declared to be normally distributed. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS assistance, to test the structural model that had been built theoretically. Before the analysis is carried out, assumption tests (analysis requirements) are carried out starting from normality, homogeneity, linearity and various other requirements required when analyzing with SPSS. The test results with SPSS are presented in tabular form.

4. Results/findings

RQ 1: is there an effect between political literacy on decisions on the use of political rights?

The first hypothesis (H₁) of this study states that there is a significant influence between the mastery of political literacy on decisions on the use of political rights of the community in Kediri Regency 2019. The results of data analysis in order to answer the formulation of problem number 1 as has been done in the data analysis process can be seen in the following table.

Table 3: R test results, mastery of political literacy (X) on decisions on the use of political rights (Y)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate
1	,727 ^a	,526	,526	2,314

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

Table 4: Results of the t test, Political Literacy (X) on decisions on the use of political rights (Y)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10,528	1,292		14,318	,000
	Political literacy	,132	,024	,303	6,543	,000

a. Dependent Variable: decisions on the use of political rights

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

Based on the calculation of the data analysis, the calculated r coefficient is 0.727, $r^2 = 0.528$ (52.8%), adjusted R 0.526 (52.6%), t is 14.318, with a significance of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded that, there is a significant influence between the mastery of political literacy on decisions on the use of political rights. The contribution of the political literacy variable to decisions on the use of political rights is .526 (52.6%). Political literacy has an influence on decisions on the use of political rights. This implies that in order to increase decisions on the use of political rights, the role of increasing community political literacy has a very large role.

RQ 2: Is there a significant influence between political maturity on decisions on the use of political rights?

The second hypothesis (H_2) states that there is a significant influence between the political maturities on the decision to use political rights in Kediri Regency 2019.

The results of data analysis related to political maturity on decisions to use political rights can be seen in the following table.

Table 5: R test results, the effect of political maturity (X) on decisions on Decision on the use of political rights (Y₂)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,427 ^a	,183	,178	1,712
a. Predictors: (Constant): political maturity				

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

Table 6: Results of the t test,, the effect of political maturity (X) on decisions on the use of political rights (Y₂)

Model Summary						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2,129	1,077		6,278	,039
	political maturity	,063	,018	,146	3,513	,001
a. Dependent Variable: Decision on the use of political rights						

Source: Analysis Data by SPSS 19.0, 2021

Based on the calculation of SPSS data analysis, the calculated r coefficient is 0.427, $r^2 = 0.183$ (18.3%), adjusted R 0.178 (17.8%), t is 6.278, with a significance of 0.039. Thus it can be concluded that, there is a significant influence between the political maturity on decisions on the use of political rights. The contribution of the political maturity variable to the decision to use political rights is .183 (18.3%). The results of this study indicate that political maturity has an influence on decisions to use political rights 0.183 (18.3%).

RQ 3: Is there an influence between political literacy and political maturity on decisions on the use political rights?

The third hypothesis (H_3) of this research is that there is a significant influence between the level of political literacy and political maturity on the decision on the use political right. The analysis results are shown in the following table.

Table 7: Political literacy and political maturity on decisions on the use political rights

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.874 ^a	.764	.761	.43248
a. Predictors: (Constant), political_maturity, political_literacy				

Source: Data processed in 2021.

Based on table 7, it is known that the mutual influence between political literacy and political maturity on the decision to use political rights is .874. Thus, the two variables together contributed to the decision to use political rights by .764 or 76.4%, while the remaining 23.6% was influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

Table 8: Double F-regression coefficient two predictors

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	110.012	2	55.006	294.084	.000 ^b
	Residual	34.042	182	.187		
	Total	144.054	184			
a. Dependent Variable: use_political_right						
b. Predictors: (Constant), political_maturity, political_literacy						

Source: Data processed in 2021

Table 8 shows that the magnitude of the F-regression coefficient on the influence model of political literacy and political maturity simultaneously on the use of political rights is (F-reg

= 294,084) with a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. So that the research model, the joint influence of political literacy and political maturity together influences the use of political rights, can be accepted...

Table 9: Significance test (t-test)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.556	.893		2.863	.005
	political_literacy	.130	.097	.125	1.336	.183
	political_maturity	.766	.094	.758	8.121	.000
a. Dependent Variable: use_political_right						

Source: Data processed in 2021

Table 9 shows the magnitude of the significance test (t-test) of 2.863 with a significance of 0.005 < 0.05, thus the joint effect of political literacy and political maturity on the use of political rights is significant. This means that the model is feasible to use. In other words, to increase political participation in the form of the use of political rights, it can be done by increasing political literacy and political maturity.

5. Discussion

5.1. The Influence of Political Literacy on Decisions on the Use of Political Rights

Based on the calculation of the data analysis, the calculated r coefficient is 0.727, $r^2 = 0.528$ (52.8%), adjusted R 0.526 (52.6%), t is 14.318, with a significance of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded that, there is a significant influence between the mastery of political literacy on decisions on the use of political rights. The contribution of the political literacy variable to decisions on the use of political rights is .526 (52.6%).

Political literacy has an influence on decisions on the use of political rights. This is in accordance with the results of research by Sutisna (2017) which explains that the better political literacy the higher the decisions on the use of political rights of voters in participating in general elections. The results of this study are also in accordance with the opinion that good political literacy will be able to increase political maturity (Bakhtiyar, 2018).

Sukmajati (2019) also reveals that political literacy controlled by a person will be able to increase their decisions on the use of political rights, in the sense that the choices they provide when selecting legislative candidates as well as candidates for local and national leaders are very rational. The results of this study also strengthen the results of Waluyo (2004) study which states that decisions on the use of political rights will be better when their literacy increases. Budijanto (2016) also explains that when a person's political literacy increases, their decisions on the use of political rights will be very wise and everything is done with careful consideration, not just using emotion.

Donnelly's (2008) research results are also corroborated by this study which reveals that good political literacy will greatly affect a person's decisions on the use of political rights. Even though there is money politics, their political choices are not affected. Kimbal (2018) also concluded that good political literacy will be able to increase the decisions on the use of political rights of a voter. Voters with political literacy will be choosing their representatives in the people's representative council and leader.

5.2. Political maturity and Decisions on the Use of Political Rights

Based on the calculation of SPSS data analysis, the calculated r coefficient is 0.427, $r^2 = 0.183$ (18.3%), adjusted R 0.178 (17.8%), t is 6.278, with a significance of 0.039. Thus it can be concluded that, there is a significant influence between the political maturity on decisions on the use of political rights. The contribution of the political maturity variable to the decision to use political rights is .183 (18.3%). The results of this study indicate that political maturity has an influence on decisions to use political rights 0.183 (18.3%). Therefore political maturity has more meaning in increasing decision on the use of political rights.

In the general elections, when it is about to increase the political participation rate, the most significant step taken is to increase the political maturity of the community. This finding support by Rosser and Diermen (2015). They state that political support maturity, the legal and democratic framework, must go hand in hand and facilitate the fulfillment of the socio-economic rights of Indonesian citizens.

The results of this study are also in accordance with the findings of Gunawan (2008) that the more mature a person is in politics, the wiser he is in making decisions to exercise his voting rights. Krampen (2000) also concluded that political maturity has a very good effect on increasing decisions on the use of political rights owned by voters. The results of this study are in accordance with the findings of Manan (2013) that when a person's political maturity is ripe, the decision to use political rights is also better, not affected by money politics, or un-educative politics of fighting against one another.

The results of this study also corroborate the findings of Handoyo (2003) that a person's decision to exercise political rights is strongly influenced by their political maturity. Those who are more mature in politics will be wiser in making decisions to use their political rights.

Likewise, Nasution & Marwandiato, (2019) also concluded that the better the political maturity of voters in general elections, the better the political decisions they use. They will not be quickly provoked by false propaganda. Nimmo, (1993) concluded that when a person's political maturity is ripe, their ability to exercise their political rights will also mature. Ready, (2016) in this case also concluded that the decision to use the political rights of a voter will be greatly influenced by his political maturity. Ahadi (2017) if someone does not use their voting rights, it means that person does not have good political maturity. Budimansyah & Suryadi (2008) state if they have good political maturity, it can be ascertained that their awareness of using their voting rights will increase. Likewise, Sondakh, (2014) in conducting a study concluded that the decision to use political rights owned by voters is very much influenced by their political maturity. Wasistiono (2003) also concluded the same thing, that

when someone uses their property rights wisely, it can be ascertained that they have good political maturity.

5.3. Political Literacy and political maturity on Decisions on the Use of Political Rights

The simultaneous influence of political literacy and political maturity on the decision to use political rights is .874. Thus, the two variables together contributed to the decision to use political rights by .764 or 76.4%, while the remaining 23.6% was influenced by other variables not included in this research model.

The results of this study reinforce the findings of Mas (2004) that good political literacy and political maturity will be able to increase decisions in the use of political rights. Bawamenewi (2019) also explains that political literacy and political maturity has a very good role in improving political decisions to use political rights. The results of this study also support the results of Budiardjo's (2010) research that political literacy and political maturity contributes to increasing decisions to the use political rights.

The results of this study are also able to strengthen previous research put forward by Sukmajati, (2019) that decisions on the use of political rights can be influenced by political literacy and by political maturity. In other words, political literacy and political maturity can improve decisions on the use of political rights. Neundorf & Smets (2020) concluded that the political literacy and political maturity will ultimately be able to increase decisions in political participation.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and referring to the formulation of the problem, it can be concluded that: (1) political literacy has a significant effect on decisions on the use of political rights, (2) political maturity has a significant influence on the use of political rights, and (3) political literacy and political maturity simultaneously (together) significantly influence the decision to use political rights.

Future researchers can also conduct research using other variables related to decisions on the use of political rights, such as the type of work, level of education, insight into character, and others. This research implies that when it comes to increasing political maturity, the essential aspect of improving is the mastery of political literacy. Likewise, when you want to increase voter turnout, you must also increase the political literacy of the community (voters).

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